

SIZE EFFECTS OF SiC PARTICLES ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CAST CARBON NANOFIBERS REINFORCED AZ91 MAGNESIUM COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Carbon nanofibers, Silicon carbide, AZ91 magnesium alloy, Metal matrix composites (MMCs), Liquid process, Mechanical properties*

1 Introduction

Magnesium alloys are attractive for industrial applications due to their low density, good damping capacity, and castability. However, their low modulus, low strength, and poor thermal stability have restricted the structural application. Magnesium matrix composites come into the spotlight to solve the problem of magnesium alloy.

Nano carbon materials such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs), carbon nanofibers (CNFs), and graphene have been promising reinforcements for light metallic matrices due to their excellent specific strength, specific modulus, and thermal and electrical conductivities [1-2]. However, fabrication of nano carbons reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs) is very challenging due to their poor wettability [3]. Because of the difficulties in introducing carbon materials into metal melts, most work used powder metallurgy (PM) techniques [4].

When fabricating nano carbons reinforced metal matrix composites (MMCs), they are critical to disperse the nano carbons in metallic melt and to maintain the stability of nano carbons under atmosphere due to strong reactivity of carbon with oxygen. In order to improve the stability of nano carbons and the wettability between nano carbons and metallic melt, Nano carbons have been coated with metal and/or oxide. The squeeze casting process, one of conventional casting methods for composites, has merits such as high productivity and easiness for near-net-shape fabrication, but has shortcomings of poor reliability, requirement of high-pressure loading of 50 MPa or more in order to enhance the wettability between reinforcements and matrix. To effectively fabricate the metal matrix composites reinforced with nano carbons, it is thus necessary to introduce new-concept fabricating

processes, one of which is a liquid pressing process [5-6] using low pressure near to the theoretically required minimum loading pressure.

Nano carbons reinforced AZ91 magnesium (Mg) alloy composites have been fabricated successfully by the uniform mixture of nano carbons and SiC particles and the unique casting method of liquid pressing process [5]. The three different sizes (0.5 μm , 3.5 μm , 10 μm) of SiC_p were uniformly mixed with CNFs by wet mixing process coupled with surfactant. In liquid pressing process, AZ91 alloy melts have been pressed hydrostatically and infiltrated on nano carbons surfaces. Microstructures of the composites have been analyzed. The mixture of CNFs and SiC_p were dispersed homogeneously in the matrix. Their mechanical properties have also been evaluated by tensile and compressive tests.

2 Experimental

The vapor grown carbon nanofibers (CNFs) supplied by Showa Denko (Japan) were used as the reinforcements. Also, silicon carbide (SiC) particles supplied by Nilaco (Japan) were additional reinforcement. AZ91 magnesium alloy was a matrix.

Table 1 Physical and mechanical properties of CNFs, SiC_p and AZ91.

Materials	Density	Elastic Modulus [GPa]	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Diameter [nm]	Length [μm]
CNF	2.0	240 ~ 400	3,000	150~200	~10
SiC	3.21	430	-	-	0.5
AZ91	1.81	45	~ 180	-	-

Fig. 1. SEM micrographs of (a) as-received CNFs, (b) silicon carbide particles (SiC_p), and (c) AZ91 magnesium alloy.

Table 1 shows the summary of physical and mechanical properties of CNFs, SiC_p and AZ91 magnesium alloy.

The uniform mixture of CNFs and SiC_p was prepared by simple sonication process with surfactant. Firstly, the ethanol suspension (1 L) of carbon nanofibers of 25.0 g was prepared by sonication for 30 min. After preparing the CNFs suspension, silicon carbide particles of 79.25 g were added and then sonicated again for 30 min. Finally, 25.0 g of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide was added and mixed by sonication for 1 hr. The mixture of CNFs and SiC_p was obtained by filtrating suspension, washing by ethanol, and drying in vacuum oven for 12 hrs.

The three different sized SiC_p (20 vol. %) and CNFs (10 vol. %) reinforced composites were fabricated by the liquid pressing process. The mold interior was sized by diameter ϕ 120 mm \times thickness t 10 mm. The CNFs and the prepared mixture of CNFs and SiC_p particles were inserted with AZ91 master alloy plates into the mold, degassed, and evacuated by a mechanical vacuum pump. The mold was heated to 720°C , held for 5 minutes, and then pressed under a pressure of below 20 MPa. The fabricated composites were sectioned, polished for scanning electron microscope (SEM) observations. The composites were also machined into sub-sized dog-bone and rectangular shape specimens for tensile and compressive tests.

3 Results and discussion

The wetting angle between carbon and magnesium is about 150° at 700°C . In case of aluminium melt on carbon substrate, the wetting angle is over 160° . The wettability of magnesium indicates that the fabrication of the carbon nano particles reinforced magnesium matrix composites is relatively easier than that of aluminium matrix composites even though it is a very difficult task by a conventional casting route. Carbides such as silicon carbide (SiC) and titanium carbide (TiC) is also not wettable with magnesium melt, but the wetting angle between the carbides and magnesium melt is much lower than that of carbon. It is anticipated that mixing SiC particles and/or TiC particles with nano carbons can be a simple and effective route to overcome the problem of casing process to make the carbon nanoparticles reinforced Mg matrix composites.

Fig. 2. Schematic of compaction and infiltration mechanism of non-wettable reinforcing particles in metallic melt.

Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram of compaction and infiltration mechanism of non-wettable (wetting angle > 90°) reinforcing particles in metallic melt. As pressure applied in the melt, the particles are compacted and the volume fraction increases. Above the critical infiltration pressure, the metallic melt is infiltrated into the gap among the compacted particles, and then the particles are swelled.

Fig. 3 shows the results of minimum infiltration pressure of Mg alloy melt into nano carbon preforms. From preliminary experiments of fraction of the preform of nano carbons increased approximately 55% due to compaction by applied pressure. In case of a change in particle size at wetting angle of 120°, the minimum infiltration pressures of CNTs (15nm) and CNFs (150nm) were about 30MPa and 3MPa, respectively. As a decrease of wetting angle of 120° at same particle size of 15 nm, the infiltration pressure decreased from about 50MPa to 30MPa.

Fig. 3. Calculated results of minimum infiltration of magnesium alloy melt into nano carbon preforms as functions of surface tension at wetting angle of 150° and particle size of 15nm, article size at wetting angle of 120°, and wetting angle at particle size of 15nm

Fig. 4. SEM images of dispersed and mechanically mixed CNFs with (a) 0.5 μm SiC_p, (b) 3.5 μm SiC_p and (c) 10 μm SiC_p.

Fig. 4 shows the images of mixture of CNFs and different sized SiC_p. The uniform distribution of SiC_p and CNFs is critical to fabricate a sound AZ91

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of of three different sized SiC_p and CNFs reinforced AZ91 composite; (a) CNFs + 0.5 μm SiC_p/AZ91, (b) CNFs + 3.5 μm SiC_p/AZ91 and (c) CNFs + 10 μm SiC_p/AZ91.

matrix composites, but is not easy because of the different density of SiC_p and CNFs. The figures show that the uniform mixture of CNFs and SiC_p was prepared successfully by wet mixing process with surfactant. Entanglements of as-received

Table 2. Mechanical properties (elastic modulus, tensile strength, and compressive strength) of three different sized SiC_p and CNFs reinforced AZ91 composites as well as AZ91 alloy.

Specimen	Elastic modulus (Gpa)	Tensile strength (Mpa)	Compressive strength (MPa)
AZ91 Mg alloy	45	170	274
CNF+0.5 mm SiC _p /AZ91	76	190	702
CNF+3.5 mm SiC _p /AZ91	75	210	580
CNF+10 mm SiC _p /AZ91	74	180	516

CNFs were separated. Also, CNFs are uniformly dispersed with SiC_p.

Fig. 5 shows the SEM images of three different composites. The reinforcements of CNFs and SiC were homogeneously distributed in the AZ91 matrix. The defects formed by misinfiltration or reaction products formed by interfacial reaction at fiber/matrix interfaces are hardly found. Table 2 summarizes the tensile and compressive properties of the composites. The elastic moduli of three CNFs + SiC_p/AZ91 composites are about 1.65 times higher than that of AZ91. The elastic modulus of CNFs + 0.5 μm SiC_p reinforced AZ91 is 76 GPa which is highest value of all. Also, the compressive strengths of composites were also much higher from CNFs and SiC_p reinforcements, even though the tensile strength was increased slightly.

4 Summary

Carbon nano fibers (CNFs) reinforced magnesium alloy (AZ91) matrix composites have been fabricated by liquid pressing process. In order to improve the dispersibility of CNFs and the wettability with magnesium alloy melt, CNFs were mixed with submicron sized SiC particles. Three different sized SiC_p and CNFs reinforced AZ91 magnesium composites were fabricated by liquid pressing process. The reinforcements were dispersed homogeneously. The mechanical properties of modulus, tensile strength, and compressive strength were improved than those of AZ91 magnesium alloy. Especially, CNF + 0.5 μm SiC_p/AZ91 composite had the highest modulus and compressive strength of all because of the excellent load dispersion by fine and well-dispersed CNF + SiC particles.

Acknowledgement

“This research was supported by a grant from the Fundamental R&D Program for Technology of World Premier Materials funded by the Ministry of Knowledge Economy, Republic of Korea”

References

- [1] M. Endo, Y.A. Kim, T. Hayashi, K. Nishimura, T. Matusita, K. Miyashita, and M.S. Dresselhaus “Vapor-grown carbon fibers (VGCFs): Basic properties and their battery applications”. *Carbon* Vol. 39, pp. 1287-1289, 2001.
- [2] M.T. Hung, O. Choi, Y.S. Ju, and H.T. Hahn “Heat conduction in graphite-nanoplatelet-reinforced polymer nanocomposites”. *Appl. Phys. Lett.*, Vol. 89, pp. 023117, 2006.
- [3] Jon M. Molina-Aldareguia and M. Reyes Elizalde “Metal Matrix Composites reinforced with nano-size reinforcements”. *Compo. Sci. Tech.*, Vol. 70, pp. 2227-2230, 2010.
- [4] R. George, K.T. Kashyap, R. Rahul, and S. Yamdagni “Strengthening in carbon nanotube/aluminium (CNT/Al) composites”. *Scripta Mater.*, Vol. 53, pp. 1159-1163, 2005.
- [5] S.B. Lee, K. Matsunaga, Y. Ikuhara, and S.K. Lee “Effect of alloying elements on the interfacial bonding strength and electric conductivity of carbon nano-fiber reinforced Cu matrix composites”. *Mater. Sci. Eng. A*, Vol. 449, pp. 778-781, 2007.
- [6] S.B. Lee S.B. S.K. Lee, S. Lee, and N.J. Kim “Microstructure and Mechanical Properties of Two Continuous-Fiber-Reinforced Zr-Based Amorphous Alloy Composites Fabricated by Liquid Pressing Process”. *Metall. Mater. Trans. A*, Vol. 39, pp. 763-771, 2008.